

GREEN COATING EFFECT ESTABLISHED IN THE ARAL SEA DRYER

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Abstract. *The given article presents information regarding forest reclamation works carried out from 2018 to 2024, as well as the volume of areas covered by green cover for the period up to the present day, in order to improve the climate balance of the arid zone of the Aral Sea. Including small aircraft (hang glider) and special equipment, as well as hand-planted saxaul, karabarak, fish eye, sarsazan, shora and other halophytic plants, which today bear fruit and spread their seeds, restore the natural phytocenosis of the area and the biodiversity of the ecosystem. It is claimed that this gives the effect of its stabilization. At the same time, it is predicted that over time, highly saline lands with a difficult melioration state will change in a positive direction, based on the periodicity of the law of nature.*

Keywords: *15-38 km of the Aral Sea, seed germination on average from 15% to 35%, water outflow (1970-1980), planting of halophytic plants.*

It is important to suggest that in the process of climate change in the world, in the process of monitoring the duration of precipitation in some regions, floods are observed. In some regions, the area of deserts is expanding due to drought and a decrease in sea water. This drought (drying up of the Aral Sea) did not spare our republic.

According to Ismanov Abduvakhob Jurayevich and et al, since the 1960s of the last century, the sharp decrease in the level of the Aral Sea has decreased by 22 meters, the amount of salt in the water has reached 112 g / l, and in the eastern part of the Aral Sea it reached 280-328 g / l. Initially, the area of the dry bottom of the Aral Sea, deprived of water, is 3.5 million hectares and in the adjacent territories, dust, sand and salt have become a source of aerosol dispersion, and the amount of dust is growing into the atmosphere is 80-100 million hectares per year. It is claimed that this is up to tons [1]. It is known that in our country these sandy desert lands occupy an area of about 9.7 million hectares. The Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 in our republic defines the tasks of "creating an additional 500 thousand hectares of green spaces on the dry bottom of the Aral Sea and increasing their total area to 2.5 million hectares or 78% of the territory by the end of 2026".

Accordingly, among the types of desert plants used for landscaping in the territories of these desert regions, the most widespread are cherkez, karabarak, saxaul. In this regard, for sowing high-quality seeds, it is advisable to use a small aviation hang glider based on cutting and peeling black sax seeds.

Based on the initiative of the head of our state, in the period 2018-2024, on the dry bottom of the Aral Sea, on an area of more than 800,000 hectares, forest reclamation measures landscaping was established.

In this regard, in the course of our practical research, forest reclamation work was carried out on the dry bottom of the Aral Sea, green covers were created on the basis of small aviation.

Sufficient results were achieved in the study of the current state, assessment of the growth processes and development of desert plants planted from seeds. In 2019-2020, the average height of Saxaul trees planted to create a green cover is 1.5-3 meters.

At present time saxaul, blackberries and other halophytic plants produce seeds and spread them, participating in the restoration of the landscape, natural phytocoenosis of the area.

Figure 1. A view of a saxaul field bearing seeds

As a result, the ecosystem is restored on the territory and conditions for increasing biodiversity are created (a large contribution to these processes in addition to our Republic is made by systemic organizations).

In the arid zone of the Aral Sea, one can see that the saxaul and plants planted from young seedlings have today turned into rough groves. 12 km from it, 10-15 thousand hectares, between 32-37 km, 38 km (right side), depending on soil conditions (gypsum and very black salt), seeds sown on the ground with white sandalwood had an average germination of 30-40%, of which an average area of 5-15 thousand hectares is occupied by black salt and highly saline soils. Saxaul plants grow alone on the ground.

In 2024, the seeds of the Saxaul were sown on an area of about 71,000 hectares using small hang glider on both sides of the road at 15-38 km of the Aral Sea. In order to strengthen the sands and build a green cover, the germination of the seeds we sow fluctuates on average from 15% to 35% (the percentage of germination varies in different areas), in some areas, that is, within 15%. As we have already mentioned above, 10-15 thousand hectares of extremely strong blackness are areas with saline soils and no plants at all. In some areas, you can see how the Saxaul sprouted from the seeds turn green.

Definitely, the periodicity of the existence of factors, based on the criteria of the laws of nature, is variable depending on its existence, the prelude to this is the biological processes of time. According to the law discovered by M. V. Lomonosov in 1741-1745, the unity of the laws of conservation of mass and energy is the law of conservation of matter. The law of conservation of energy, like the law of conservation of mass, is one of the fundamental laws of nature. In his work "Elements of Mathematical Chemistry" the scientist wrote that the cause of change in matter is the movement of particles of matter [2].

According to these physical laws, conservation of energy, conservation of matter, conservation of mass processes really exists, only mass and content change over time.

Therefore, matter does not disappear and does not exist out of nothing, when one type of matter disappears, another type of matter appears. It provides information about the conservation of matter

1-2 pictures. Biennial plants-saxaul and fish eye (fish eye is an annual herb).

Figure 3. Seedlings of 1-2-year-old saxaul on sandy brackish islands.

Figure 4. Single seedlings of marsh black salt marsh- saxaul.

It can be concluded that due to the change in the soil structure of the island region (see Fig. 3), stepwise germination of seeds is observed on the sandy islands. In the region (see Fig. 4), there are highly saline black solon etic soils, the sown seeds remain in the soil and die, and the structure of these black-saline (highly acidic) soils undergoes a process of compositional change over time. This takes time in accordance with the biological laws of nature. It is well known that water intake mainly began during the period of the former Soviet Union (1970-1980). Now, step by step, the soil composition of the land freed from the water that has receded over the years is improving as a result of the action of biological factors. The growth of planted halophytic plants is observed, therefore, perennial planting of halophytic plants (saxaul, karabarak, balikkoz, sarsazan, shora) on the land freed from water gives its results. As a result, sand-dust and salt storms observed in the Aralbay district will be prevented and the amount of fine sand particles in the air will decrease. This will increase the biodiversity of the flora and fauna of the district, and as a result, the well-being of the population will be ensured.

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